

SWACHH BHARAT ABHIYAN: IMPACT OF INCREASED CLEANLINESS ON THE INDIAN ECONOMY

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Abstract:

India the seventh largest country by area and the second most populous country with over 1.2 billion people is the most populous democracy in the world. Currently, India one of the fastest growing major economies, faces many environmental problems and issues caused by poor hygiene and lack of sanitation in the country. The 17 Sustainable Development Goals are interlinked Global Goals which are designed as a blueprint to achieve a better and more sustainable future for people world over. There are interlinkages between each of these 17 sustainable goals, as Goal No. 6 of clean water and hygiene is a shared responsibility and has huge impact on the health, pollution and also climate of any nation. As a World Bank report in 2006 said that India losses 6.4 percent of GDP annually because of poor hygiene and sanitation. Unhygienic conditions are one of the major causes of diseases. A UN report in May had said that currently, nearly 60 percent of India's population practice open-defecation which puts them at risk of diseases like cholera, diarrhea, typhoid etc. Swachh Bharat Abhiyan (Clean India Mission) is a national campaign by the Government of India, covering more than 4,000 cities and towns, to clean the streets, roads and infrastructure of the country. This paper looks at the impact of increased emphasis on cleanliness on the Indian economy in terms of Gross Domestic Product growth, reduction in health care costs, and a source of employment.

Key Words: *Swachh Bharat Abhiyan, Sanitation, Environmental Protection, Indian Economy, Economic Development*

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Introduction

"The pursuit of cleanliness can be an economic activity, contributing to GDP growth, reduction in healthcare costs, and a source of employment. The sustainable development of one-sixth of humanity will be of great consequence to the world and our beautiful planet."

~ Shri. Narendra Modi, Prime Minister of India

Indian economy is undergoing a state of disruptive flux with political initiatives like demonetization, increased emphasis on cashless transactions, GST etc. as well as the pandemic. Yet, Swachh Bharat Abhiyan is one key initiative by the government which can impact the society as well as public health and thereby the economic development. Globally, India has the highest number of people practicing open defecation. Close to 60 percent of the number of people globally who do not have toilets and defecate in the open, live in India, who has 17.5 percent of the world's population. Shri. Narendra Modi, the Prime Minister of India launched Swachh Bharat Abhiyan (Clean India Mission) on 2nd Oct. 2014. This national campaign by the Government of India covers more than 4,000 cities and towns, to clean the streets, roads and infrastructure of the country. The campaign aims to remove open defecation by 2019 in India, by 2nd October, 2019 which is the 150th birth anniversary of Mahatma Gandhi.

India along with other countries signed the declaration on the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, comprising of seventeen Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) at the Sustainable Development Summit of the United Nations in September 2015. The 17 Sustainable Development Goals are intertwined Global Goals, which are designed as a proposal to achieve a better and more sustainable future for people world over. There are interlinkages between each of these 17 sustainable goals, as Goal No. 6 of clean water and hygiene is a shared responsibility and has huge impact on the health, pollution and also climate of any nation. The following policies further summarizes India's progress across the SDGs:

1. **Sashakt Bharat - Sabal Bharat (Empowered and Resilient India):** is an initiative towards the development of a pan India platform to lift more than 271 million people out of multidimensional poverty towards economic growth and empowerment.
2. **Swachh Bharat - Swasth Bharat (Clean and Healthy India):** A nationwide initiative activated by the Clean India Campaign and the National Nutrition Mission, for sanitation and Universal health coverage.

3. **Samagra Bharat - Saksham Bharat (Inclusive and Entrepreneurial India):** A nationwide initiative for Social and Financial inclusion through Jan Dhan-Aadhaar-Mobile (JAM) trinity.
4. **Satat Bharat – Sanatan Bharat (Sustainable India):** A national climate action strategy for planned eco-restoration, building disaster resilient infrastructure, and building clean and efficient energy systems.
5. **Sampanna Bharat- Samriddh Bharat (Prosperous and Vibrant India):** India's initiative to become a USD 5 trillion economy by 2025, by pursuing an inclusive and sustainable growth trajectory through stimulating manufacturing, infrastructure-building, fostering technological innovation through investments and boosting entrepreneurship.

The **Swachh Bharat** national campaign aims at linking hygiene and cleanliness to tourism and tries to bring about a paradigm shift in the global perception and interest in India. The Prime Minister has said world class levels of hygiene and cleanliness are required to make India among the top 50 tourist destination and to bring about a paradigm shift in the global perception about the country. The Prime Minister has said that the quest of cleanliness can be an economic activity, leading to growth in Gross Domestic Product, decrease in health care expenses and a source of employment.

Swachh Bharat Abhiyan was developed at a sanitation conference organized by UNICEF India and the Indian Institute of Technology as part of the larger Total Sanitation Campaign in March 2014.¹ The Indian government aims to achieve an Open-Defecation Free (ODF) India by 2 October 2019, the 150th anniversary of the birth of Mahatma Gandhi, by constructing 12 million toilets in rural India at a projected cost of ` 1.96 lakh crore (US\$31 billion).² The programme has also received funds and technical support from the World Bank, from various corporate social responsibility initiatives, and under the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan and Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan schemes.

Need for a National Campaign like Swachh Bharat Abhiyan

Sanitation is broadly defined to include management of human wastes, solid waste, and its drainage. An UN report stated that nearly 60 per cent of India's population practice

¹ Sharda, S. (2017). *Poo2loo to break open defecation taboo - Times of India*. [online] The Times of India. Available at: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/lucknow/Poo2loo-to-break-open-defecation-taboo/articleshow/31542256.cms> [Accessed 29 Dec. 2017].

² Standard, B. (2017). MDWS Intensifies Efforts with States to Implement Swachh Bharat Mission. [online] Business-standard.com. Available at: http://www.business-standard.com/article/government-press-release/mdws-intensifies-efforts-with-states-to-implement-swachh-bharat-mission-116031801084_1.html [Accessed 29 Dec. 2017].

open-defecation leading to a lack of cleanliness and hygienic conditions, which increases the risk of diseases like cholera, diarrhea, typhoid etc. According to a World Bank report India also face economic losses of Rs. 2.4 Trillion (US\$53.8 Billion) annually equivalent of 6.4 percent of GDP in 2006, because of sanitation and unhygienic conditions in the country.

Open-defecation is the practice of defecating outside or in public and may be done as a result of cultural practices or having no access to toilets. However, this practice carries a significant health risk and becomes an issue for human dignity when it occurs in more densely populated areas, of large villages or in urban informal settlements especially in developing countries. Under such circumstances the practice is usually associated with poverty and exclusion. Globally more than one billion people do not have access to toilets, and 60 percent of this number are Indians with the majority coming from rural areas.

Open-defecation practices remain a huge health and safety risk, and issues associated with practice will escalate as India's population grows. The negative impact of lack of hygiene caused by lack of proper sanitation is given below:

Public Health

The negative public health impacts of open defecation are considerable with huge costs to the economy. Open defecation is an important factor that cause various diseases; the most common being diarrhea, typhoid, cholera, hepatitis, polio, trachoma etc. Lack of sanitation and unsafe water is considered responsible for one of the heaviest existing disease burdens worldwide and accounts for about 10% of the global burden of disease.³ India as a dense populated especially in rural areas lead to open defecation in fields, leading to contamination of water and food. Experts warn that open-defecation lead to ingestion of human waste, either because it has contaminated the food or water supplies or because it has been spread by flies and dust.

According to the joint UNICEF and the World Health Organization report, the absence of toilets remains one of the leading causes of illness and death among children, especially diarrhea, a disease often associated with poor sanitary conditions, result in the death of many children under the age of five annually. Young children are debilitated

³ Van Minh, H. and Hung, N. (2017). Economic Aspects of Sanitation in Developing Countries. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3212862/> [Accessed 29 Dec. 2017].

due to persistent diarrheal episodes become more vulnerable to malnutrition and opportunistic infections such as pneumonia.⁴

Safety of Women

Open defecation due to inadequate sanitation has been linked to serious health consequences which go beyond ill health for women and girls. Lack of safe, private toilets makes women and girls defenseless and more susceptible to violence and this often acts as an impediment to girls' education. Women in their search for secluded and private places for open defecation purposes are at risk of sexual violence especially during hours of darkness.⁵ Sanitation policies have to recognize women's specific sanitation needs like the privacy required during menstruation, the changed bladder and bowel movements during pregnancy and more.

Objectives of Swachh Bharat Abhiyan

Swachh Bharat Abhiyan tries to plug this loss and help to ease the burden on existing health care facilities which will help to boost our Indian economy. The national mission of Swachh Bharat Abhiyan has the following main objectives:

1. Elimination of Open Defecation among the Population and thereby to prevent the spread of diseases like Diarrhea, Cholera etc
2. To bring about a Behavioral Change in people's attitude and create awareness among people towards the importance of cleanliness as well as good sanitation system and its linkage with public health
3. To stamp out manual scavenging.
4. To develop rural areas by developing the sanitation system and to construct toilets for community and houses to eliminate open defecation.
5. To introduce modern and scientific municipal solid waste management practices for the betterment of the Indian economy.

⁴ Nayyar, S. (2017). *Sanitation, Health and Hygiene in India*. [online] Health Issues India. Available at: <https://www.healthissuesindia.com/2014/02/05/sanitation-health-hygiene-india/> [Accessed 29 Dec. 2017].

⁵ Anand, A. (2017). Lack of toilets puts India's health and rural women's safety at risk. [online] the Guardian. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/global-development/2014/aug/28/toilets-india-health-rural-women-safety> [Accessed 29 Dec. 2017].

The Swachh Bharat Abhiyan has the Following Components:

Benefits of Swachh Bharat Abhiyan:

Poor sanitation affects health leading to high levels of malnutrition and consequent productivity losses. At the same time as reducing open defecation and ensuring increased access to toilets in every home is crucial, it is also necessary to improve ‘environmental sanitation’ to include waste management of all types. Rapid population growth and industrialization has increased the quantity of wastes from residential areas, industries and other settings exponentially. Benefits of improved sanitation extend well beyond reducing the risk of diarrhea and these include:

- reducing the spread of tropical diseases like intestinal worms, schistosomiasis and trachoma;
- reducing the severity and impact of malnutrition;
- endorsing dignity and boosting safety, particularly among women and girls;
- encouraging school attendance: girls’ school attendance is particularly boosted by the provision of separate sanitary facilities; and
- potential cleanup of water, renewable energy and nutrients from fecal waste.

❖ **Public Health**

The diseases linked with poor sanitation, hygiene, and unsafe water is predominantly associated with poverty and infancy and account for about 10% of the worldwide burden of disease. Improving sanitation has vital impact not only on health, but on social and economic development, predominantly in developing countries. The economic benefits of improved sanitation include reduced health care costs, fewer days

of absenteeism at work or school and also the convenience of saving time in search for sanitation facilities. The social benefits of improved sanitation include creating physical environments that enhance safety, dignity and self-esteem. Safety issues are chiefly important for women as well as children, who often risk sexual violence while defecating at night and in secluded areas. Furthermore, for women, the availability of household sanitation reduces the risk of sexual violence, and for girls, the provision of school sanitation facilities means less days of absence from school during menstruation. Also, improving sanitation facilities and promoting hygiene in schools, benefits both learning and the health of children and help to retain students, especially girls.

❖ **Tourism**

India has a rich cultural heritage and even more richer history. Tourism generates approximately 6.6% of India's GDP and many millions are directly employed in this sector. According to experts, lack of cleanliness acts as the biggest impediment in promoting tourism as foreign tourists are put off by the unhygienic and insanitary conditions. Swachh Bharat Mission will help to generate more employment opportunities through tourism and thereby boost India's GDP and transforming the country.

❖ **Clean Technology**

Increased emphasis on cleanliness and hygiene will shift focus towards use of clean technology which is non-polluting in nature and will help to generate more employment / entrepreneurial opportunities and more future technological development. Swachh Bharat Mission will not only bring in an environment of cleanliness and hygiene but it can also put India in the league of skilled economies of the world.

❖ **Individual Productivity**

Developed countries with good sanitation are excellent examples which show that healthy citizens can help in increasing per capita GDP of the country while an underdeveloped nation with poor sanitation and hygiene will have more unhealthy citizens with lower productivity and thereby will always remain under developed or developing nation. Swachh Bharat Mission will to create a Healthy India which in turn increase productivity of Indians and lead to the economic prosperity of the nation.

❖ **Foreign Direct Investment**

Foreign direct investment is important for India's future development, as it helps to increase the availability of capital for investment purposes leading to increased economic growth which helps to generate more employment opportunities and reduce poverty and raise living standards in the country. Swachh Bharat Mission can help to encourage "healthier and more wholesome social conditions India" by improving environmental conditions would not only enhance the quality of life for Indians and cultivate national pride, but also attract foreign investors and tourists to India.

❖ **Better Environment**

Cleaner communities would lead to less illnesses, thus creating the necessary social conditions for higher economic growth through industry and tourism. Thus, Swachh Bharat Mission will have a positive impact in the future by tackling many issues such as mosquitoes, pollution, inconsiderate littering, street hawkers and sanitation.

Challenges Faced by Swachh Bharat Abhiyan

Access to sanitation increases health, well-being and economic productivity and is a key development intervention – without sanitation, ill-health rules a life without dignity and self-esteem. Inadequate provision of sanitation affects individuals, households, communities and countries. Yet, in spite of its importance, achieving real gains in sanitation coverage has been slow in the country. As of December 2016, over 27 Lakh Household toilets and more than 1.28 lakh Community toilet blocks have been constructed under the urban mission.

Several factors, practical and cultural, inhibit toilet usage. Lack of water and sewerage connections, unhygienic condition of the toilets due to the fact that many households share one latrine, poor construction quality and lax maintenance, difficulties with managing fecal sludge, difficulty faced by the disabled in using these toilets, all combine to either prevent toilets from being used consistently, or force people to relapse into open defecation as the toilets become unusable. The government has certainly made the toilets but it is still struggling to bring in a behavioral change in the rural population, as several villagers in the country use the toilets to keep feed of their cattle and still practice open defecation. Although the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan lays a lot of emphasis on collecting waste in cities, it does not seem to have given adequate attention to waste management.⁶

⁶ Bhuyan, R. (2017). The real challenge for Swachh Bharat Abhiyan. [online] <http://www.livemint.com/>. Available at: <http://www.livemint.com/Home-Page/NhOIZRnRvpF6w64UWbFJFP/The-real-challenge-for-Swachh-Bharat-Abhiyan.html> [Accessed 29 Dec. 2017].

Most of the solid waste generated in cities is dumped in landfill sites, which apart from being health hazards, also pose a serious threat to land and water resources.

Conclusion

The fight for a much cleaner, greener and healthier India can only succeed with a proper framework to manage the generation, management and disposal of waste. The Indian Government aims to achieve access to adequate and equitable sanitation and hygiene for all and end open defecation, paying special attention to the needs of women and girls and those in vulnerable situations by 2030. Sanitation is a complex topic, with linkages to health as well as social and economic development. It affects all but is championed by few. Inadequate sanitation affects public health and thereby the economy of country. Hence, improving sanitation is the most effective way of reducing these losses. A clean and safe environment is a prerequisite to healthier nation which help to generate more economic development. But this will require proper strategies like ensuring political will and leadership by establishing obvious institutional responsibility and adequate budget for sanitation along with collective participation by the public authorities working in health, in water resources, and in utility services. It also requires involving the health sector in sanitation and transforming sanitation sector according to the needs of the people by inherently addressing the problem of affordability.

Proper sanitation is the key to social and economic development of the nation as it helps to prevent the contamination of scarce water resources, prevent the spread of infectious diseases which in turn reduces the malnutrition and stunting in children as well as protects the environment. Good sanitation helps to protect the dignity and wellbeing of women and girls and fight ill health. Swachh Bharat Abhiyan aims to change people's perception of and behavior towards cleanliness and though may have shortcomings for various logistical and social reasons. Yet, this programme by improving the outreach and acceptability has far reaching consequences for the economy of the nation.

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